

Evaluation of Patient's Satisfaction at the Out-patient Department (OPD) of the CMH (Combined Military Hospital) in Savar Cantonment, Savar, Dhaka

Md. Shahinur Rahman, Md. Abu Talha

Bangladesh Open University (NHF&RI)

ABSTRACT

Introduction: patient satisfaction surveys are essential in obtaining a comprehensive understanding of the patient's need and their opinion of the service received. It is a vital tool in evaluation the quality of the healthcare delivery service in hospital. **Research methodology:** the current study is a cross-sectional descriptive study about evaluation of patient satisfaction at the out-patient department (opd) of the cmh (combined military hospital) in savar cantonment, savar, dhaka. The study population respondents aged 18 years and above, 100 respondents were interviewed by using a questionnaire from january to april, 2021, excluding public holidays. The respondents were asked about the basic information of socio-demographic characteristics, facilities at opd, dealings of service providers, clinical examination, treatment cost. This study aimed to assess the level of patient satisfaction with opd services among the patient in the cmh (combined military hospital) in savar cantonment, savar, dhaka. **Result:** the average results of patient satisfaction were majority of the patients had satisfied in adequacy and comfort in sitting arrangement, cooling arrangement, drinking water facility, and overall cleanliness of opd. About 91% respondents were satisfied in doctor patient's relationship, 71% satisfied in nurse patient's relationship, 85% satisfied in maintaining privacy, 83% respondents were satisfied in time given for consultation. 84% satisfied given treatment. 79% respondents were satisfied about sterilization, 56% satisfied in procedure cost. Some respondents were dissatisfied from cleanliness of toilet (59%), 72% dissatisfied for long waiting time and 60% were dissatisfied in long time required for treatment procedure. **Conclusion:** From these findings, it is evident that the determination of the satisfaction is very complex. It involves trust, patient characteristics and need as well as their perception to physicians and interpersonal skill. Patient satisfaction assessment should be regular assignment of all hospitals that should be conducted. It will be helpful in keep knowing the problems of patient's and improving the quality of care, ultimately earning good name and prestige for institution.

Keywords: Patient satisfaction, Out-patient Department (OPD), CMH (Combined Military Hospital).

INTRODUCTION

Patient satisfaction is easy to understand but difficult to define, however patient satisfaction can be defined by keegan. The patient satisfaction reflects the total experience of health care. According to Swamy, patient satisfaction is the real testimony to the efficiency of hospital administration. Kotler defined satisfaction as a person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment resulting from comparing a product's perceived performance or outcome, in relation to his or her expectation. Dansky and miles states that from a management perspective, client satisfaction with healthcare is important for two reasons, first, satisfied patients are more likely to maintain a consistent relationship with a specific provider and second, by identifying sources of patient satisfaction, an

organization can address system weakness, thus improving its risk management

LITERATURE REVIEWS:

Riser pointed out that patient satisfaction has been defined as the degree of congruency between a patient's expectation of ideal nursing care and his perception of real nursing care he receives. In another study by Giese *et. al.*, it was determined that when examining satisfaction as a whole, three general components can be identified: patient satisfaction as a response (emotional or cognitive), 2) the response pertains to a particular focus (expectation, product, consumption, experience etc.) and the response occurs at a particular time (after consumption, after choice, based on accumulated experience etc.) A study was held on 400 adult patients on the out-patient department of a typical Taiwanese hospital and aim of

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this study was to propose a conceptual framework for identifying the key drivers and provide guidance for enhancing out-patient care service quality.

METHODOLOGY

The survey was conducted in out-patients Department CMH (Combined Military Hospital) Savar cantonment, Savar, Dhaka. Studies of 100 patients were taken in the study from the out-patient department of the CMH (Combined Military Hospital), Savar Cantonment, Savar, Dhaka. A questionnaire consisting of 34 question taken from both female and male aged 18 and above who were willing for study and informed consent was taken from the patient who had undergone the study.

1. Study objectives: to assess the level of patient satisfactinon with OPD services among the patient in the CMH (Combined Military Hospital) Savar cantonment, Savar, Dhaka.
2. Study Design: This study was a cross sectional study.
3. Study site and area: The survey was conducted at the out-patient department of this study was a cross sectional descriptive study.
4. Study population: The target population was patients attending the OPD.
5. Study period: The duration of the study was January to April, 2020.
6. Study size: We were estimate the proportion with 5% discrepancy with 95% confidence. Due to some constraint of the investigator and lake of time, the sample size fix at 100 purposively.
7. Sample technique: These study was conducted by using the purposive sampling method.
8. Ethical consideration: The study had ethical approval from the ethical committee of the Bangladesh Open University
9. Limitation: the study was conducted only one CMH.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Distribution Patients according to their sex (n=100)

sex	No of patient	Percentage %
Male	63	63%
Female	37	37%

Out of patients surveyed, most of the patients (67%) were male, and rest of the patients (37%) were female.

2. Distribution of patients according to their marital status (n=100).

Status	Number of patient	Percentages %
Married	60	60%
Unmarried	30	30%
Widowed	9	9%
Separated	1	1%
Divorced	0	0
Others	0	0

In table 2 shows distribution of patients according to their marital status. About 60% patients were married, 30% unmarried, 9% windowed and 1% separated.

3. Distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding adequacy of sitting arrangement for OPD (n=100)

Satisfaction level	Number of patient	Percentage %
Satisfied	88	88%
Dissatisfied	12	12%

Table 3 shows distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding adequacy of sitting arrangement for OPD. Most of the patients (88%) were satisfied and 12% patients were dissatisfied about adequacy of sitting arrangement.

4. Distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding adequacy of cooling arrangement for OPD (n=100).

Satisfaction level	Number of patient	Percentage %
Satisfied	69	69%
Dissatisfied	31	31%

Table 4 shows distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding adequacy of cooling arrangement for OPD. Most of the patients (69%) were satisfied and 31% patients were dissatisfied about adequacy of cooling arrangement.

5. Distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding adequate supply of safe drinking water (n=100).

Satisfaction level	Number of patient	Percentage %
Satisfied	76	76%
Dissatisfied	24	24%

Table 5 shows distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding adequate supply of safe drinking water. Most of the patients (76%) were satisfied and 24% patients were dissatisfied about adequate supply of safe drinking water.

6. Distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding availability of toilets for patients (n=100)

Satisfaction level	Number of patient	Percentage %
Satisfied	66	66%
Dissatisfied	34	34%

Table 6 shows distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding availability of toilets for patients in waiting area of OPD. Most of the patients (66%) were satisfied and 34% patients were dissatisfied.

7. Distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding opinion about doctor patient's relationship (n=100).

Satisfaction level	Number of patient	Percentage %
Satisfied	91	91%
Dissatisfied	9	9%

Table 7 shows distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding opinion about doctor patient's relationship. Most of the patients (91%) were satisfied and 9% patients were dissatisfied.

8. Distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding maintaining privacy (n=100)

Satisfaction level	Number of patient	Percentage %
Satisfied	85	85%
Dissatisfied	15	15%

Table 8 shows distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding maintaining privacy. Most of the patients (88%) were satisfied and 12% patients were dissatisfied.

9. Distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding the waiting time (n=100)

Satisfaction level	Number of patient	Percentage %
Satisfied	72	72%
Dissatisfied	28	28%

Table 9 shows distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding the waiting time. Most of the

patients (72%) were satisfied and 28% the waiting time % patients were dissatisfied.

10. Distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding the length of time needed for procedure (n=100)

Satisfaction level	Number of patient	Percentage %
Satisfied	60	60%
Dissatisfied	40	40%

Table 10 shows distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding the length of time needed for procedure. Most of the patients (60%) were satisfied and 40% patients were dissatisfied.

11. Distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding satisfaction of the treatment (n=100).

Satisfaction level	Number of patient	Percentage %
Satisfied	86	86%
Dissatisfied	14	14%

Table 11 shows distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding satisfaction of the treatment. Most of the patients (88%) were satisfied and 12% patients were dissatisfied.

12. Distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding procedure cost (n=100).

Satisfaction level	Number of patient	Percentage %
Satisfied	56	56%
Dissatisfied	44	44%

The bar graph shows distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding procedure cost (n=100). Table 12 shows distribution of patients according to satisfaction regarding procedure cost of the treatment. Most of the patients (56%) were satisfied and 44% patients were dissatisfied.

DISCUSSION

This study shows, maximum patients about 80% patients were satisfied with comfort in sitting arrangement, 74% patients were satisfied regarding overall cleanliness of OPD and 87% patients were satisfied on drinking water facility for OPD and 86% patients were satisfied on their treatment. In the term of patients experience at king khalid university college of dentistry (KKU/CD) clinics-Abha, Saudi Arabia, it is re-assuring to observe that 99.3% and 91% patients respectively rated the clinic reception area good to excellent as far as comfort and cleanliness were concerned. All participating patients were generally satisfied with arrangement of their appointments. The results related to satisfaction of the patient about treatment cost, 68% were satisfied on transport cost for reaching the hospital. A study was held on Ajman University, United Arab Emirates where 57% of the patients were complaints that the dental clinic was too far from their house.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Evaluation of patient's satisfaction should be done regularly by the organization or the hospitals by conducting such survey for the propose of continuous improvement. By conducting such study one can able to understand the difference between patient demands

and patient's satisfaction. The survey also helps to find the deficiencies and weakness of the health care and also helps to evaluate the effect of effort to improve health care services. Providing the care with physical comfort, emotional support, respecting the patient's preferences, with communication, information, education result in a high quality of treatment and patient's satisfaction. Finally, a good understanding can only develop when patients were assumed with service quality. The increase in service quality is not the only solution, quality must also be considered. So, it needs regularly assessment of all hospitals. it will be helpful in keeping knowing the problems of patients and improving the quality of care, ultimately earning good name and prestige for the institution.

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